

Conic and Cyclidic Sections in Double Conformal Geometric Algebra $\mathcal{G}_{8,2}$ with Computing and Visualization using Gaalop*

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August 3, 2019

Abstract

The $\mathcal{G}_{8,2}$ Geometric Algebra, also called the Double Conformal / Darboux Cyclide Geometric Algebra (DCGA), has entities that represent conic sections. DCGA also has entities that represent planar sections of Darboux cyclides, which are called cyclidic sections in this paper. This paper presents these entities and many operations on them, in terms of algebraic expressions, computer code and many examples of computer generated graphics. Operations include reflection, projection, rejection, and intersection with respect to spheres and planes. Other operations include rotation, translation, and dilation. Possible applications are introduced that include orthographic and perspective projections of conic sections onto view planes, which may be of interest in computer graphics or other computational geometry subjects.

Keywords: conformal geometric algebra, conic sections, perspective projection, geometric algebra computing, visualization

Mathematics Subject Classification: 15A66, 14H50, 53A30

1 Introduction

The Geometric Algebra $\mathcal{G}_{8,2}$, called the Double Conformal / Darboux Cyclide Geometric Algebra (DCGA), is introduced in [3] [4] [5]. This paper presents some additional results in DCGA for representing conic and cyclidic sections and for geometrically operating on conic and cyclidic sections in DCGA.

Conic sections have long been studied by famous mathematicians and innumerable researchers, over many generations going back thousands of years, and are usually represented by compass-ruler constructions in synthetic geometry

*E. H. humbly requests to respect the *Creative Peace License* [17] when applying the research presented in this paper.

or by general quadratic equations in algebraic geometry. Much is known about conic sections, but new methods of computation with conic sections may still be valuable in future applications. Using Clifford geometric algebra, it is possible to find many new computational representations of conic sections. This paper introduces a particular new representation of conic and cyclidic sections in general position in 3D space as 4-vectors (in the sense of [7]) in DCGA. This new representation also comes with a complete set of conformal geometric transformation operators, which are the CGA versors for reflections in planes, inversions in spheres, rotations, translations, and dilations (uniform scalings) in 3D space. Further geometric operations include contractions, intersections with planes and spheres, projections of conic sections onto planes and spheres, rejections of conic sections from planes and spheres, and differentiation (see [5]). A new method for the orthographic and perspective projection of conic sections in 3D space is introduced, which includes a new method for computing the general elliptic double cone of a conic section with a given vertex (eye) point. The cone of a conic section represents the line-of-sight of rays passing from an eye to a point of a conic section. Intersecting the cone with another plane produces a perspective projection. The new computational 4-vector representation may motivate or enable future applications and further research. The fully computational operations for orthographic and perspective projections of entire conic sections could have some immediate applications in computer graphics or computational geometry.

Conic sections and meet intersections were studied in conformal geometric algebra in [14]. The following sections of this paper elaborate on the conic and cyclidic sections with many illustrative figures produced using the Geometric Algebra Computing software called the Geometric Algebra Algorithms Optimizer *Gaalop* that is introduced in [11] and [13]. First, Section 2 introduces basic concepts of Conformal Geometric Algebra (CGA), and Section 3 presents some fundamentals of DCGA. Next, Section 4 explains the notion of sections in DCGA. Moreover, Section 5 introduces geometric operations on sections in DCGA. Then, Section 6 shows two examples how the new framework for conic and cyclidic sections in DCGA can be applied. We conclude with Section 7. Finally, in Appendix A, it is explained how to use the *Gaalop Visualizer* to visualize DCGA entities. The *Gaalop Visualizer* is introduced in [21], it is based on *CLUViz* [19]. At the time of writing this paper, *Gaalop* appeared to be a very unique software for its ability to render visualizations of the DCGA conic and cyclidic section entities.

2 Conformal Geometric Algebra (CGA)

For a general introduction to W.K. Clifford's geometric algebra, we refer the reader to [16, 8, 7]. We briefly review the concepts of conformal geometric algebra (CGA)[10, 2, 11, 13, 15], in order to introduce the necessary notation for constructing double CGA (DCGA). The CGA1 \mathcal{C}^1 and CGA2 \mathcal{C}^2 entities follow the ordinary $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$ *Conformal Geometric Algebra*.

2.1 CGA point entity

The $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$ CGA null 1-vector *point*

$$\mathbf{P}_C = \mathcal{C}(\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E}) = \mathcal{C}_{4,1}(\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E}) = \mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E} + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E}^2\mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_o \quad (2.1)$$

is derived by stereographic embedding and homogenization of the point $\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E}$ [20]. The Euclidean 3D point $\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E}$ in \mathcal{G}_3 APS \mathcal{E} is $\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E} = p_x\mathbf{e}_1 + p_y\mathbf{e}_2 + p_z\mathbf{e}_3$. In $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$ CGA, the point at the origin \mathbf{e}_o and at infinity \mathbf{e}_∞ are

$$\mathbf{e}_o = \frac{1}{2}(-\mathbf{e}_4 + \mathbf{e}_5), \quad \mathbf{e}_\infty = \mathbf{e}_4 + \mathbf{e}_5. \quad (2.2)$$

The elements \mathbf{e}_4 and \mathbf{e}_5 are sometimes denoted $\mathbf{e}_+ \cong \mathbf{e}_4$ and $\mathbf{e}_- \cong \mathbf{e}_5$ since $\mathbf{e}_4^2 = +1$ and $\mathbf{e}_5^2 = -1$.

A normalized (*unit scale*) point, with unit scale on the component \mathbf{e}_o , is

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}_C = \mathbf{P}_C / (-\mathbf{P}_C \cdot \mathbf{e}_\infty) = \mathcal{C}(\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E}). \quad (2.3)$$

The *projection* (inverse embedding) of a point $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_C = \mathcal{C}(\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E})$ is

$$\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E} = (\hat{\mathbf{P}}_C \cdot \mathbf{I}_\mathcal{E})\mathbf{I}_\mathcal{E}^{-1}, \quad (2.4)$$

where the \mathcal{G}_3 APS \mathcal{E} unit pseudoscalar is $\mathbf{I}_\mathcal{E} = \mathbf{I}_\mathcal{E}^1$.

2.2 CGA IPNS surface entities

A CGA point $\mathbf{T}_C = \mathcal{C}(\mathbf{t}_\mathcal{E}) = \mathcal{C}_{4,1}(\mathbf{t}_\mathcal{E})$ is on a CGA *geometric inner product null space* (IPNS) surface \mathbf{S}_C iff $\mathbf{T}_C \cdot \mathbf{S}_C = 0$ [20]. The CGA IPNS *sphere* vector \mathbf{S}_C , centered at CGA point $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_C = \mathcal{C}(\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E})$, with radius r or through CGA point $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_C = \mathcal{C}(\mathbf{q}_\mathcal{E})$, is defined as

$$\mathbf{S}_C = \hat{\mathbf{S}}_C = \hat{\mathbf{P}}_C - \frac{1}{2}r^2\mathbf{e}_\infty = \hat{\mathbf{P}}_C + (\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_C \cdot \hat{\mathbf{P}}_C)\mathbf{e}_\infty. \quad (2.5)$$

Formed with normalized points $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_C$ and $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_C$ (2.3), the sphere is *unit scale* $\mathbf{S}_C = \hat{\mathbf{S}}_C$, where $\hat{\mathbf{S}}_C^2 = r^2$. The CGA IPNS *plane* vector $\mathbf{\Pi}_C$, normal to unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_\mathcal{E}$, at distance d from the origin or through 3D point $\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E}$, is defined as

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_C = \hat{\mathbf{\Pi}}_C = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_\mathcal{E} + d\mathbf{e}_\infty = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_\mathcal{E} + (\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_\mathcal{E})\mathbf{e}_\infty. \quad (2.6)$$

Formed with unit normal vector $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_\mathcal{E}$, the plane is *unit scale* $\mathbf{\Pi}_C = \hat{\mathbf{\Pi}}_C$, where $\hat{\mathbf{\Pi}}_C^2 = 1$.

The CGA IPNS 2-blade *line* \mathbf{L}_C , in the direction of the unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_\mathcal{E}$, perpendicular to unit bivector $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_\mathcal{E}^* = \hat{\mathbf{d}}_\mathcal{E}^*\mathbf{I}_\mathcal{E} = \hat{\mathbf{d}}_\mathcal{E}/\mathbf{I}_\mathcal{E}$, and through Euclidean 3D point $\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E}$, is defined as

$$\mathbf{L}_C = \hat{\mathbf{L}}_C = \hat{\mathbf{d}}_\mathcal{E}^* - (\mathbf{p}_\mathcal{E} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{d}}_\mathcal{E}^*)\mathbf{e}_\infty. \quad (2.7)$$

Formed with unit direction vector $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_\mathcal{E}$, the line is *unit scale* $\mathbf{L}_C = \hat{\mathbf{L}}_C$, where $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_C^2 = -1$. The line \mathbf{L}_C can be factored into the intersection of two planes as $\mathbf{L}_C = \mathbf{\Pi}_{C_1} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}_{C_2}$. The CGA IPNS 2-blade *circle* $\mathbf{C}_C = \mathbf{S}_C \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}_C$, is the intersection of a sphere \mathbf{S}_C and plane $\mathbf{\Pi}_C$.

2.3 CGA versor operations

Any *versor* V for reflections, rotations, translations and dilations, respectively, operates on any *entity* \mathbf{X} using the *versor “sandwich” operation*

$$\mathbf{X}' = V\mathbf{X}V^{-1}. \quad (2.8)$$

The even parity CGA 2-versors $V_{\mathcal{C}^k}$ have unimodular exponential forms e^A such that their *reverse* $V_{\mathcal{C}^k}^\sim$ equals their inverse $V_{\mathcal{C}^k}^{-1}$.

A k -versor V [7] can be factored into a product of k vectors as $V = \prod_{i=1}^k \mathbf{a}_i$. The versor operation may be most computationally efficient as the succession of vector reflections $\mathbf{X}' = \mathbf{a}_1(\cdots(\mathbf{a}_k\mathbf{X}\mathbf{a}_k)\cdots)\mathbf{a}_1$, which is an application of the CARTAN-DIEUDONNÉ theorem on orthogonal transformations. The vectors \mathbf{a}_i are typically the CGA IPNS plane vector $\mathbf{\Pi}_{\mathcal{C}}$ or sphere $\mathbf{S}_{\mathcal{C}}$. In general, the associativity of the geometric products in versor transformations can greatly affect the computational efficiency of the operation.

3 Double Conformal Geometric Algebra DCGA

We further briefly introduce some fundamental ideas of Double Conformal Geometric Algebra (DCGA). The first $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$ CGA subalgebra, called CGA1 \mathcal{C}^1 , is the geometric algebra of the five unit vector elements $\mathbf{e}_i : 1 \leq i \leq 5$, with $\mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_j = +1$ for $i = j, 1 \leq i \leq 4$, $\mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_j = -1$ for $i = j = 5$, and zero otherwise. The second $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$ CGA subalgebra, called CGA2 \mathcal{C}^2 , is defined similarly with the unit vector elements $\mathbf{e}_i : 6 \leq i \leq 10$. The CGA1 \mathcal{C}^1 and CGA2 \mathcal{C}^2 unit pseudoscalars are

$$\mathbf{I}_{\mathcal{C}^1} = \mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_4\mathbf{e}_5, \quad \mathbf{I}_{\mathcal{C}^2} = \mathbf{e}_6\mathbf{e}_7\mathbf{e}_8\mathbf{e}_9\mathbf{e}_{10}. \quad (3.1)$$

The $\mathcal{G}_{8,2}$ DCGA metric is therefore

$$m = \text{diag}(1, 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, 1, 1, -1) = [m_{ij}] = [\mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_j]. \quad (3.2)$$

The DCGA \mathcal{D} unit pseudoscalar is $\mathbf{I}_{\mathcal{D}} = \mathbf{I}_{\mathcal{C}^1}\mathbf{I}_{\mathcal{C}^2} = \mathbf{I}_{\mathcal{C}^1} \wedge \mathbf{I}_{\mathcal{C}^2}$. For the indexing scheme $\mathbf{X}_{\mathcal{C}^k}$, $k \in \{1, 2\}$ indicates an element \mathbf{X} of CGA1 or CGA2, and i is an iterator. A Euclidean 3D vector $\mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{E}^1}$ in the \mathcal{G}_3 *Algebra of Physical Space*¹ 1 (APS1) \mathcal{E}^1 [8], subalgebra of $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$ CGA1 \mathcal{C}^1 , is formed with conventional $(x, y, z) \cong (p_x, p_y, p_z)$ scalar components as

$$\mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{E}^1} = p_x\mathbf{e}_1 + p_y\mathbf{e}_2 + p_z\mathbf{e}_3, \quad \mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{E}^2} = p_x\mathbf{e}_6 + p_y\mathbf{e}_7 + p_z\mathbf{e}_8 \quad (3.3)$$

and its paired copy or double $\mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{E}^2}$ in the \mathcal{G}_3 APS2 \mathcal{E}^2 subalgebra of $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$ CGA2 \mathcal{C}^2 . The \mathcal{G}_3 APS1 \mathcal{E}^1 and \mathcal{G}_3 APS2 \mathcal{E}^2 unit pseudoscalars are $\mathbf{I}_{\mathcal{E}^1} = \mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_3$, and $\mathbf{I}_{\mathcal{E}^2} = \mathbf{e}_6\mathbf{e}_7\mathbf{e}_8$, respectively. CGA1 \mathcal{C}^1 and CGA2 \mathcal{C}^2 are paired copies or doubles. Any CGA entity², versor, or pseudoscalar $A_{\mathcal{C}^k}$ in CGA1 as $A_{\mathcal{C}^1}$ is paired with identical scalar components on corresponding elements in CGA2 as $A_{\mathcal{C}^2}$, and their geometric or outer product $A_{\mathcal{D}} = A_{\mathcal{C}^1}A_{\mathcal{C}^2} = A_{\mathcal{C}^1} \wedge A_{\mathcal{C}^2}$, is

¹The algebra of physical space can be interpreted as the algebra of directions in space. It uses measured directions from the origin to denote locations, as opposed to a separate algebraic concept of points. We do thank the anonymous reviewer for this helpful clarification.

²An entity, or *geometric entity*, is a multivector that represents a point, curve, or surface.

the corresponding doubled DCGA \mathcal{D} entity, versor, or pseudoscalar $A_{\mathcal{D}}$. The doubled DCGA \mathcal{D} entities $\mathbf{X}_{\mathcal{D}} = A_{\mathcal{D}}$ are called the DCGA *standard entities* or *bi-CGA entities* $\mathbf{X}_{\mathcal{D}}$. For example, the DCGA *standard* 2-blade point entity $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}}$ is the double CGA point, $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}} = \mathbf{P}_{C^1} \wedge \mathbf{P}_{C^2}$.

The DCGA point $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}}$ is a linear combination of various basis 2-blades, each with a certain scalar coefficient. The contraction (inner product) of $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}}$ with various *reciprocal* basis 2-blades extracts certain scalar coefficients from $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}}$. As explained further in reference [5], there are 15 unique coefficients that can be extracted by contraction of $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}}$ with various 2-vector *extraction operators* (reciprocal basis 2-blades), as shown in Table 1. For example, $x = T_x \cdot \mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}}$, and generally $s = T_s \cdot \mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}}$ for index s . A linear combination of the extraction operators from Table 1 is an IPNS bivector entity $\Omega = \sum_s \alpha_s T_s$ that represents the degree-4 polynomial of an implicit Darboux cyclide surface or degenerate³ forms (i.e., some extraction operators not included in the linear combination).

$T_x = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_{\infty 2} + \mathbf{e}_{\infty 1}\mathbf{e}_6)$	$T_y = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_{\infty 2} + \mathbf{e}_{\infty 1}\mathbf{e}_7)$	$T_z = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_{\infty 2} + \mathbf{e}_{\infty 1}\mathbf{e}_8)$
$T_{x^2} = \mathbf{e}_6\mathbf{e}_1$	$T_{y^2} = \mathbf{e}_7\mathbf{e}_2$	$T_{z^2} = \mathbf{e}_8\mathbf{e}_3$
$T_{xy} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{e}_7\mathbf{e}_1 + \mathbf{e}_6\mathbf{e}_2)$	$T_{yz} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{e}_7\mathbf{e}_3 + \mathbf{e}_8\mathbf{e}_2)$	$T_{zx} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{e}_8\mathbf{e}_1 + \mathbf{e}_6\mathbf{e}_3)$
$T_{xt_{\xi}^2} = \mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_{o2} + \mathbf{e}_{o1}\mathbf{e}_6$	$T_{yt_{\xi}^2} = \mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_{o2} + \mathbf{e}_{o1}\mathbf{e}_7$	$T_{zt_{\xi}^2} = \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_{o2} + \mathbf{e}_{o1}\mathbf{e}_8$
$T_1 = -\mathbf{e}_{\infty}$	$T_{t_{\xi}^2} = \mathbf{e}_{o2}\mathbf{e}_{\infty 1} + \mathbf{e}_{\infty 2}\mathbf{e}_{o1}$	$T_{t_{\xi}^4} = -4\mathbf{e}_o$

Table 1: The DCGA bivector *extraction operators* T_s .

$\mathcal{G}_{8,2}$ DCGA extends $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$ CGA with new DCGA IPNS *bivector entities* for quartic Darboux cyclides Ω (including quartic Dupin cyclides Φ and tori \mathbf{O} , cubic parabolic cyclides Ψ , and general quadric surfaces \mathbf{Q}) as linear combinations $\Omega = \sum \alpha_s T_s$ of the DCGA extraction elements T_s (compare eq. (3.8) of [4]). A point $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}}$ is on the surface represented by Ω iff $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}} \cdot \Omega = 0$. *Doubled* (paired) CGA versors (DCGA versors) can be applied to all DCGA entities. The new DCGA IPNS bivector entities can be intersected (by wedge product) with doubled CGA IPNS entities (DCGA IPNS entities), but the new DCGA IPNS bivector entities cannot be intersected with each other by means of a meet operator as in CGA [14], since they are generally not represented by blades.

4 DCGA section representation

Conformal geometric algebra in its modern form started with the work of D. Hestenes [9] [10]. The concepts and definitions of (geometric) inner product null space (IPNS) and (geometric) outer product null space (OPNS) *entities* are explained in detail by Perwass in [20]. In this paper, all geometric entities are IPNS entities in DCGA.

The DCGA IPNS bivector two-dimensional (*2D*)-*surface* entity Υ is generally defined in [3] as an instance of the DCGA IPNS bivector *Darboux cyclide* surface entity Ω or alternatively as an instance of a *degenerate* form of Ω .

The first degenerate forms are the DCGA IPNS bivector *Dupin cyclide* surface entity Φ and the DCGA bivector *horned Dupin cyclide* surface entity Γ .

³We use the term *degenerate* informally, or loosely, to mean lower forms of the Darboux cyclide polynomial, which includes Dupin cyclides, Blum cyclides, and certain lower-degree surfaces such as degree-3 parabolic cyclides, general degree-2 quadrics, and further "degenerate" forms that are linear (or factorisable into linear factors).

The next degenerate form is the DCGA IPNS bivector *parabolic cyclide* surface entity Ψ . Further degenerates of the parabolic cyclide entity Ψ are the DCGA bivector quadric surface entities. The Darboux cyclide Ω and Dupin cyclide Φ , Γ entities are generally quartic surfaces. The parabolic cyclide Ψ entity is generally a cubic surface.

All of the DCGA IPNS *2D-surface* entities Υ can be intersected with a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *plane* entity Π or with a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *sphere* entity \mathbf{S} . The DCGA IPNS quadvector *intersection* one-dimensional (1D) line entity $\Upsilon \wedge \Pi$ can also be called a DCGA IPNS *section* entity

$$\psi = \Upsilon \wedge \Pi. \quad (4.1)$$

A *1D-surface* on a plane is also called a *plane curve*. The degree of a plane curve or section ψ depends on the degree of the 2D-surface Υ it is cut from. A section of a quartic surface $\Upsilon = \Omega$, Φ or Γ is a quartic plane curve.

A section of a cubic surface, such as a parabolic cyclide Ψ , is a cubic plane curve. A section of a quadric surface, such as a cone \mathbf{K} , is a quadratic plane curve, also called a *conic section*.

A DCGA IPNS quadvector *section* plane 1D curve entity ψ is defined as the intersection (4.1) of a DCGA IPNS bivector *2D-surface* entity Υ and a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *plane* entity Π .

As a special case, if Υ is a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *sphere* \mathbf{S} or *plane* Π , then $\psi = \Upsilon \wedge \Pi$ is either a standard DCGA IPNS quadvector *circle* entity \mathbf{C} or a standard DCGA IPNS quadvector *line* entity \mathbf{L} . These entities are special since in our model they can be further intersected with each other, while other entities cannot be intersected with each other. These are special conic sections of a standard sphere or plane.

4.1 Conic sections in DCGA

Conic sections are planar cuts through a quadric cone surface. A *conic section* is an ellipse, parabola, hyperbola, line, non-parallel lines pair, or the cone vertex point. Planar cuts through other quadric surfaces, such as ellipsoid, hyperboloid, and paraboloid, can produce some of the conic section quadratic plane curves, but not all of them.

The DCGA IPNS quadvector *conic section* quadratic 1D-surface plane-curve entity κ is defined as the intersection

$$\kappa = \mathbf{K} \wedge \Pi \quad (4.2)$$

of a DCGA IPNS bivector *cone* quadric 2D-surface entity \mathbf{K} and a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *plane* entity Π . The cone entity \mathbf{K} is a degenerate form of the parabolic cyclide entity Ψ .

Figure 1 shows some DCGA *conic section* entities $\epsilon, \rho, \eta, \chi$ rendered by the Gaalop Visualizer. The conic section entities are intersections $\mathbf{K} \wedge \Pi$ of various standard DCGA *plane* entities Π with a DCGA *cone* entity \mathbf{K} .

For example, in [3] and [5], the ellipse $\epsilon^{\parallel xy} = \mathbf{H}^{\parallel z} \wedge \Pi^{z=0}$, parabola $\rho^{\parallel xy} = \mathbf{B}^{\parallel z} \wedge \Pi^{z=0}$, and hyperbola $\eta^{\parallel xy} = \mathbf{J}^{\parallel z} \wedge \Pi^{z=0}$ in the *xy*-plane ($z = 0$) are defined as the intersection of the *xy*-plane $\Pi^{z=0}$ with a *z*-axis aligned elliptic cylinder $\mathbf{H}^{\parallel z}$, parabolic cylinder $\mathbf{B}^{\parallel z}$, and hyperbolic cylinder $\mathbf{J}^{\parallel z}$, respectively.

Figure 1: Conic sections: quadratic plane curves

4.2 Cyclidic section in DCGA

Cyclidic sections are planar cuts through Darboux cyclide, Dupin cyclide, and parabolic cyclide surfaces. Since quadric surfaces are degenerate cyclides, the cyclidic sections are a generalization of the conic sections. Cyclidic sections through Darboux cyclides and Dupin cyclides are quartic plane curves. Cyclidic sections through parabolic cyclides are cubic plane curves. Conic sections through degenerate parabolic cyclides are quadratic or linear plane curves. The general cyclidic section can be represented by the intersection of a Darboux cyclide and plane.

The DCGA IPNS quadvector *cyclidic section* quartic 1D-surface plane-curve entity ω is defined as the intersection

$$\omega = \Omega \wedge \Pi \quad (4.3)$$

of a DCGA IPNS bivector *Darboux cyclide* quartic 2D-surface entity Ω and a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *plane* entity Π .

The entity Ω may be a degenerate form that includes Dupin cyclides Φ, Γ and parabolic cyclides Ψ , but not degenerate parabolic cyclides or quadric surfaces.

A *cyclidic section* entity ω represents either a quartic or cubic plane curve. A quadratic or linear plane curve is a *conic section* entity κ , which may also be called a *degenerate cyclidic section*.

Figure 2 shows an example of a cyclidic section that is a quartic plane curve. The DCGA *ring Dupin cyclide* Φ ($R = 3, r_1 = 1, r_2 = 2$) is cut by a DCGA plane Π_i ($\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{e}_3, d = 0$) that is rotated 25° around the x -axis \mathbf{e}_1 using a DCGA rotor R operation as $\Pi = R\Pi_i R^\sim$. The cyclidic section entity is the intersection entity $\omega = \Phi \wedge \Pi$.

Figure 3 shows an example of a cyclidic section that is a cubic plane curve. The DCGA IPNS bivector *parabolic cyclide* $\Psi = \mathbf{SOS}^\sim$ is the DCGA IPNS

Figure 2: Cyclidic section: quartic plane curve

Figure 3: Cyclidic section: cubic plane curve

bivector *toroid* \mathbf{O} ($R = 3, r = 2$) reflected in the standard DCGA bivector *sphere* \mathbf{S} ($\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{e}_1, r = 2$). The sphere \mathbf{S} center point $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}} = \mathcal{D}(\mathbf{p})$ is on the toroid \mathbf{O} surface, and the parabolic cyclide Ψ is the *inversion* of the toroid \mathbf{O} in the sphere \mathbf{S} . The cyclidic section $\Psi \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ is the intersection of the parabolic cyclide Ψ and a standard DCGA *plane* $\mathbf{\Pi}$ ($\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{e}_3, d = 0$) that is rotated 25° around the x -axis \mathbf{e}_1 .

5 Operations on sections in DCGA

Operations on DCGA IPNS general section entities ψ include: *reflection* of ψ in a sphere \mathbf{S} or plane $\mathbf{\Pi}$, *projection* of ψ onto a sphere \mathbf{S} or plane $\mathbf{\Pi}$, *rejection* of ψ from a sphere \mathbf{S} or plane $\mathbf{\Pi}$, *intersection* of ψ with a sphere \mathbf{S} or plane $\mathbf{\Pi}$, and general *rotation*, *translation*, and *dilation*.

The reflection in a sphere is also known as inversion in a sphere. Inversion of a curve in a sphere produces the curve with points that are at an inverse displacement from the sphere center point when the sphere radius is $r = 1$, which is as expected. Reflection of a curve in a plane produces the reflected image of the curve on the opposite side of the reflection plane, which is also as expected.

The projection is a spherical or orthographic projection *onto* a sphere or plane surface, respectively. The inversion and projection of a curve point *in* and *onto* a sphere are collinear, on a line from the center of the sphere to the curve point. A curve point projects onto a sphere where the line through the curve point and its inverse point intersects the sphere surface. The projection line also passes through the sphere center point. A curve point projects onto a plane where the line through the curve point and its reflected point intersects the plane surface, and the projected point is midway between the curve point and its reflected point.

The rejection is a perpendicular projection of a curve or surface from a sphere or plane, and it emerges at 90° or *normal to* the sphere or plane when the curve or surface and the sphere or plane have an intersection. The rejection produces a projected curve on the surface of a perpendicular plane or perpendicular sphere through intersection points. The rejection of a surface from a plane or sphere produces a rejected surface that is perpendicular. For example, an ellipsoid that intersects a plane can be rejected from the plane to produce an elliptic cylinder representing the ellipse cut through the ellipsoid by the plane.

The intersection of the section entities ψ with each other in general, not just with standard DCGA planes, spheres, lines, and circles, *would be* a very useful operation but unfortunately it does not work by way of a simple outer product operation. The DCGA intersections rule and formula is given in [5], which states that *only a single* entity that is not a standard DCGA plane $\mathbf{\Pi}$, sphere \mathbf{S} , line \mathbf{L} , or circle \mathbf{C} can be included in a wedge that forms an intersection entity. This condition still applies when forming intersections that include a DCGA IPNS section entity ψ . This means that it is possible to intersect any section entity $\psi = \Upsilon \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ with other coplanar *circles* $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{S} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ and *lines* $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{\Pi}_2 \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ as, for example, an intersection entity such as $\Upsilon \wedge \mathbf{S} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}_2 \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$, which is an 8-vector. When the common plane $\mathbf{\Pi}$ is known, it can be contracted out of entities, and the example intersection could be written as $(\psi \cdot \mathbf{\Pi}) \wedge (\mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{\Pi}) \wedge (\mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{\Pi}) \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$.

Although the operations are limited to working against only spheres and

Figure 4: Reflection (inversion) of cyclidic section ψ in sphere \mathbf{S}

planes, they still allow for many interesting possibilities to produce transformed curves and surfaces that have scientific, technical or even artistic uses. The following subsections explore these operations in more detail, with many illustrative figures rendered by the Gaalop Visualizer [11].

5.1 Reflection

The reflection ψ' of a DCGA IPNS quadvector *section* plane 1D curve ψ in a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *plane* $\mathbf{\Pi}$ is defined as

$$\psi' = \mathbf{\Pi}\psi\mathbf{\Pi}^{\sim}. \quad (5.1)$$

The reflection, also called the inversion, ψ' of a DCGA IPNS quadvector *section* plane 1D curve ψ in a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *sphere* \mathbf{S} is defined as

$$\psi' = \mathbf{S}\psi\mathbf{S}^{\sim}. \quad (5.2)$$

Figure 4 shows the reflection (inversion) of a cyclidic section in a sphere. The Gaalop Visualizer **CLUscript** for this figure is:

```
:Green;:D=DupinCyclide(3,2,1);
:Black;:P=Plane(0,0,1/2,0);
:Blue;:S=Sphere(0,0,7/2,5/2);
:Black;:DP=D^P/16;
:Black;:R=S*DP*~S/1024;
```

5.2 Projection

The projection ψ' of a DCGA IPNS quadvector *section* plane 1D curve ψ onto a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *plane* $\mathbf{\Pi}$ is defined as

$$\psi' = (\psi \cdot \mathbf{\Pi})\mathbf{\Pi}^{-1} = (\psi \cdot \mathbf{\Pi})\mathbf{\Pi}^{\sim}. \quad (5.3)$$

Figure 5: Projection of cyclidic section ψ onto sphere \mathbf{S}

The projection ψ' of a DCGA IPNS quadvector *section* plane 1D curve ψ onto a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *sphere* \mathbf{S} with radius r is defined as

$$\psi' = (\psi \cdot \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^{-1} = \frac{1}{r^4}(\psi \cdot \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^\sim. \quad (5.4)$$

Figure 5 shows the projection of a cyclidic section onto a sphere. The Gaalop Visualizer **CLUscript** for this figure is:

```
:Green;:D=DupinCyclide(3,2,1);
:Blue;:S=Sphere(1,1,7/2,5/2);
:Black;:P=Plane(0,0,1/2,0);
:Black;:DP=D^P/16;
:Black;:PRJ=(DP.S)*~S/2048;
```

5.3 Rejection

The rejection ψ' of a DCGA IPNS quadvector *section* plane 1D curve ψ from a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *plane* $\mathbf{\Pi}$ is defined as

$$\psi' = (\psi \wedge \mathbf{\Pi})\mathbf{\Pi}^{-1} = (\psi \wedge \mathbf{\Pi})\mathbf{\Pi}^\sim. \quad (5.5)$$

Figure 6: Rejection of cyclidic section ψ from sphere \mathbf{S}

The rejection ψ' of a DCGA IPNS quadvector *section* plane 1D curve ψ from a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *sphere* \mathbf{S} with radius r is defined as

$$\psi' = (\psi \wedge \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^{-1} = \frac{1}{r^4}(\psi \wedge \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^{\sim}. \quad (5.6)$$

Figure 6 shows the rejection of a cyclidic section from a sphere. The Gaalop Visualizer **CLUscript** for this figure is:

```
:Green; :D=DupinCyclide(3,2,1);
:Blue; :S=Sphere(-1,-1,1,5/2);
:Black; :P=Plane(0,0,1/2,0);
:Black; :DP=D^P/16;
:Red; :REJ=(DP^S)*~S/1024;
:Black; :SP=S^P;
```

It may be difficult to see from Fig. 6, but the rejection curve (red) intersects through the sphere at a 90° angle to the surface.

Figure 7 shows the rejection of a cyclidic section from a plane. The Gaalop Visualizer **CLUscript** for this figure is:

```
:Blue; :D=DupinCyclide(3,2,1);
:Green; :P2=Plane(1,0,2,0);
:Black; :P=Plane(0,0,1/2,0);
:Black; :DP=D^P/16;
:Red; :REJ=(DP^P2)*~P2;
```

5.4 Commutator and anti-commutator projections

The geometric product AB can be written as the sum of the anti-symmetric *commutator* product \times and the symmetric *anti-commutator* product $\bar{\times}$ as

$$AB = \frac{1}{2}(AB - BA) + \frac{1}{2}(AB + BA) = A \times B + A \bar{\times} B. \quad (5.7)$$

Given a cyclidic section ψ and a sphere \mathbf{S} (or a plane), then

$$\psi = \psi \mathbf{S} \mathbf{S}^{-1} = (\psi \times \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^{-1} + (\psi \bar{\times} \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^{-1}. \quad (5.8)$$

Figure 7: Rejection of cyclidic section ψ from plane Π_2

The *commutator projection* of ψ onto \mathbf{S} can be defined as the part

$$\psi' = (\psi \times \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^{-1}, \quad (5.9)$$

and the *anti-commutator rejection* of ψ from \mathbf{S} can be defined as the part

$$\psi' = (\psi \bar{\times} \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^{-1}. \quad (5.10)$$

For example, we look at a parabola and its reflection, projection, rejection, commutator projection, and anti-commutator rejection with respect to a sphere.

Figure 8 shows spherical operations on a parabola. The sphere \mathbf{S} , not rendered, is enclosed in the green circle and is shaded magenta. The parabola ρ is constructed as the intersection of a z -axis aligned parabolic cylinder $\mathbf{B}^{|z}$ and the xy -plane $\Pi^{z=0}$. The Gaalop Visualizer **CLUscript** for this figure is:

```
:Cyan;:C=PCylinderZ(0,0,0,1,1,1);
:Green;:P=Plane(0,0,1,0);
:Magenta;:S=Sphere(-2,0,0,5/2);
:Yellow;:CP=C^P;
:Black;:REF=S*CP*~S;
:Green;:PRJ=(CP.S)*~S;
:Red;:REJ=(CP^S)*~S;
:Orange;:COM=(CP*S-S*CP)*~S;
:Blue;:ACOM=(CP*S+S*CP)*~S;
```

If the plane $\Pi^{z=0}$ is contracted out of any of the projection or rejection plane curves, then the result is a surface that contains the plane curve. For example, the *anti-commutator rejection* plane curve can be turned into a DCGA IPNS 2D-surface Υ as

$$\Upsilon = \Pi^{z=0} \cdot ((\rho \bar{\times} \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^{-1}) = \Pi^{z=0} \rfloor ((\rho \bar{\times} \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^{-1}). \quad (5.11)$$

Figure 8: Spherical operations on a parabola ρ

5.5 Intersection

As explained in [3] and [5], all DCGA entities can be intersected only with standard DCGA spheres \mathbf{S} and planes $\mathbf{\Pi}$. The standard DCGA line $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{\Pi}_2 \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ and circle $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{S} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ are constructed from standard sphere \mathbf{S} and plane $\mathbf{\Pi}$. The set $\mathcal{S} = \{\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{\Pi}\}$ includes all instances of the *standard bi-CGA IPNS bivector entities*, which are spheres and planes. All of the plane-curve *sections* $\psi = \mathbf{\Upsilon} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ can be intersected with coplanar lines $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{\Pi}_2 \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ and circles $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{S} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$, but not with any other types of coplanar curves. Coplanar curves may intersect in four or less points in the plane $\mathbf{\Pi}$.

The DCGA IPNS 6-vector *intersection* \mathbf{X} of a DCGA IPNS quadvector *section* plane 1D curve $\psi = \mathbf{\Upsilon} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ and a coplanar standard DCGA IPNS quadvector *line* $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{\Pi}_2 \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ in the plane $\mathbf{\Pi}$ is defined as

$$\mathbf{X} = (\psi \cdot \mathbf{\Pi}) \wedge (\mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{\Pi}) \wedge \mathbf{\Pi} \simeq \mathbf{\Upsilon} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}_2 \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}. \quad (5.12)$$

The DCGA IPNS 6-vector *intersection* \mathbf{X} of a DCGA IPNS quadvector *section* plane 1D curve $\psi = \mathbf{\Upsilon} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ and a coplanar standard DCGA IPNS quadvector *circle* $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{S} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ in the plane $\mathbf{\Pi}$ is defined as

$$\mathbf{X} = (\psi \cdot \mathbf{\Pi}) \wedge (\mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{\Pi}) \wedge \mathbf{\Pi} \simeq \mathbf{\Upsilon} \wedge \mathbf{S} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}. \quad (5.13)$$

If $\gamma_1 = (\mathbf{B}_1 \in \mathcal{S}) \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ and $\gamma_2 = (\mathbf{B}_2 \in \mathcal{S}) \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ are standard DCGA IPNS quadvector *circle* \mathbf{C} or *line* \mathbf{L} , respectively, in the plane $\mathbf{\Pi}$, then their DCGA IPNS 8-vector *intersection* \mathbf{X} with a coplanar DCGA IPNS quadvector *section* 1D-surface plane-curve $\psi = \mathbf{\Upsilon} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}$ can be defined as

$$\mathbf{X} = (\psi \cdot \mathbf{\Pi}) \wedge (\gamma_1 \cdot \mathbf{\Pi}) \wedge (\gamma_2 \cdot \mathbf{\Pi}) \wedge \mathbf{\Pi} \simeq \mathbf{\Upsilon} \wedge \mathbf{B}_1 \wedge \mathbf{B}_2 \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}. \quad (5.14)$$

6 Applications

6.1 Orthographic projection of a conic section

The orthographic projection κ_{ortho} of a DCGA IPNS quadvector *conic section* $\kappa = \mathbf{K} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}_\kappa$ onto a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *plane* $\mathbf{\Pi}$ is defined as

$$\kappa_{\text{ortho}} = (\kappa \cdot \mathbf{\Pi}) \mathbf{\Pi}^{-1}. \quad (6.1)$$

Figure 9 shows an orthographic projection κ_{ortho} of an ellipse $\kappa = \epsilon$ onto a view plane $\mathbf{\Pi} = \mathbf{\Pi}^{z=0}$. The ellipse ϵ , which is constructed as the intersection of an ellipsoid and a plane, is rotated by 45° around the y -axis. The Gaalop Visualizer **CLUscript** for this figure is:

```
E=Ellipsoid(0,0,-2,3,2,1)^Plane(0,0,-1,2);
:Blue;:ER=Rotor(0,1,0,45)*E~Rotor(0,1,0,45);
:Black;:P=Plane(0,0,1,0);
:Black;:ORTHO=(ER.P)*~P;
```


Figure 9: Orthographic projection of ellipse ϵ

6.2 Perspective projection of a conic section

The perspective projection κ_{persp} of a DCGA IPNS quadvector *conic section* $\kappa = \mathbf{K} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}_{\kappa}$ onto a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *plane* $\mathbf{\Pi}$ from the view point $\mathbf{p} = x\mathbf{e}_1 + y\mathbf{e}_2 + z\mathbf{e}_3$ represented by a standard DCGA IPNS bivector *sphere* \mathbf{S} with center $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}} = \mathcal{D}(\mathbf{p})$ can be defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_{\text{persp}} &= (((\kappa \cdot \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^{-1}) \cdot \mathbf{S}) \wedge \mathbf{\Pi} \\ &= (\mathbf{S} \rfloor ((\kappa \cdot \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^{-1})) \wedge \mathbf{\Pi} = \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{p}} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}. \end{aligned} \quad (6.2)$$

The conic section κ is projected onto the sphere \mathbf{S} as $\kappa' = (\kappa \cdot \mathbf{S})\mathbf{S}^{-1}$. The sphere \mathbf{S} is contracted [2] out of κ' to form a cone $\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{p}} = \kappa' \cdot \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S} \rfloor \kappa'$. The cone $\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{p}}$ has vertex point $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}} = \mathcal{D}(\mathbf{p})$ and it contains both curves κ and κ' . The cone $\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{p}}$ is intersected with any view plane $\mathbf{\Pi}$ to form the perspective projection. The radius $r \neq 0$ of sphere \mathbf{S} is arbitrary, but $r = 1$ could be assumed.

It is also possible to use the reflection $\mathbf{S}\kappa\mathbf{S}^{-1}$ and define κ_{persp} as

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_{\text{persp}} &= ((\mathbf{S}\kappa\mathbf{S}^{-1}) \cdot \mathbf{S}) \wedge \mathbf{\Pi} \\ &= (\mathbf{S} \rfloor (\mathbf{S}\kappa\mathbf{S}^{-1})) \wedge \mathbf{\Pi} = \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{p}} \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}. \end{aligned} \quad (6.3)$$

Figure 10 shows a perspective projection κ_{persp} of a parabola $\kappa = \rho$ onto a view plane $\mathbf{\Pi}^{z=-1}$ from a view point (or eye point) $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{e}_1 + \mathbf{e}_2 + \mathbf{e}_3$ at the center $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}} = \mathcal{D}(\mathbf{p})$ of a sphere \mathbf{S} . The sphere \mathbf{S} , not rendered, is shaded. The parabola ρ is constructed as the intersection of a z -axis aligned parabolic cylinder $\mathbf{B}^{\parallel z}$ and the xy -plane $\mathbf{\Pi}^{z=-2}$. The Gaalop Visualizer **CLUscript** for this figure is:

```
:Red; :C=PCylinderZ(1,-2,-2,2,5,1)^Plane(0,0,-1,2)/8;
:Blue; :S=Sphere(1,1,1,1);
:Red; :PRJS=(C.S)*~S;
:Green; :K=PRJS.S;
:Black; :P=Plane(0,0,-1,1);
:Black; :PERSP=K^P;
```

Figure 11 shows a perspective projection κ_{persp} of an ellipse $\kappa = \epsilon$ onto a view plane $\mathbf{\Pi}^{z=-1}$ from a view point (or eye point) $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{e}_1 + \mathbf{e}_2 + \mathbf{e}_3$ at the center $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{D}} = \mathcal{D}(\mathbf{p})$ of a sphere \mathbf{S} with radius $r = 2$. The ellipse ϵ is constructed as the intersection of an ellipsoid \mathbf{E} and plane $\mathbf{\Pi}^{z=-2}$. The ellipse $\kappa = \epsilon$ is

Figure 10: Perspective projection of parabola ρ

Figure 11: Perspective projection of ellipse ϵ using reflection

reflected in the sphere \mathbf{S} as $\kappa' = \mathbf{S}\kappa\mathbf{S}^{-1}$. The cone \mathbf{K}_p is formed by contraction as $\mathbf{K}_p = \kappa' \cdot \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S} \rfloor \kappa'$. The cone \mathbf{K}_p is intersected with a view plane $\mathbf{\Pi}^{z=-1}$ to form the perspective projection $\kappa_{\text{persp}} = \mathbf{K}_p \wedge \mathbf{\Pi}^{z=-1}$. The Gaalop Visualizer **CLUscript** for this figure is:

```
:Red;:E=Ellipsoid(1,-2,-2,3,2,1)^Plane(0,0,-1,2)/8;
:Blue;:S=Sphere(1,1,1,2);
:Red;:REFS=S*E*~S;
:Green;:K=REFS.S;
:Black;:P=Plane(0,0,-1,1);
:Black;:PERSP=K^P;
```

7 Conclusion

This paper has presented the *conic section* and *cyclidic section* quadvector entities in DCGA, which are generally called DCGA *section* entities. The section entities are quartic, cubic, quadratic, or linear plane curves formed as the intersection of a plane with another surface, which can generally be any Darboux cyclide surface. This paper also presented many of the operations that are available in DCGA on section entities. The operations include *reflections*, *projections*, *rejections*, and *intersections* against spheres and planes. The operations for *rotation*, *translation*, and *dilation* in DCGA can also be applied to DCGA section entities. As possible applications, orthographic and perspective projections of conic sections were presented.

This paper has presented, or introduced, only some of the most basic results on the DCGA quadvector section entities in 3-D space; further research could be done in the future.

It is, of course, also possible to represent conic sections (general quadratic plane curves) and their inversions in circles (special cubic and quartic curves) as bivector entities in a 2-D DCGA over a 2-D Euclidean plane vector space \mathbb{R}^2 (e.g., fixing $z = 0$ in the 3-D DCGA that has been considered in this paper). However, the full theory of conic sections, as intersections of cones and planes in Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 , seems to require the quadvector entities of the 3-D DCGA over \mathbb{R}^3 , as presented in this paper.

Double CGA (DCGA, 2-CGA) is further extensible to an Extended CGA (k-CGA) $\mathcal{G}_{k(p+1),k(q+1)}$, as a product of k corresponding orthogonal CGAs (each with the same scalar coefficients on corresponding basis blades, as copies), for k -vector entities representing general degree k polynomials and their inversions (special degree $k+1$ to $2k$ polynomials) in an n -D pseudo-Euclidean space $\mathbb{R}^{p,q}$, $n = p + q$. As an example, the Triple CGA (TCGA, 3-CGA) for the Euclidean plane \mathbb{R}^2 , $\mathcal{G}_{3(2+1),3(1)} = \mathcal{G}_{9,3}$, is discussed in the paper [6].

Acknowledgments

We thank Dietmar Hildenbrand and the GAALOP development team, for developing GAALOP. We thank the anonymous reviewers for their careful reading of our manuscript, and for many helpful comments and hints. E.H. wishes to thank God: Soli Deo Gloria. This work does not have any conflicts of interest.

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A DCGA computing using Gaalop

The Geometric Algebra Algorithms Optimizer is a Geometric Algebra Computing and Visualization software developed by D. Hildenbrand et al. Hildenbrand introduces Gaalop in his books, [11] and [13], and paper [12]. The Gaalop Pre-compiler is introduced by P. Charrier in his master's thesis [1]. The Visualizer plugin for Gaalop is introduced by C. Steinmetz in his master's thesis [21].

Gaalop uses the **CLUScript** domain-specific scripting language for Geometric Algebra Algorithms that was originally written and conceived by C. Perwass as the scripting module of his CLUCALC / CLUVIZ software package. Perwass introduces CLUCalc in his book [20].

Using Gaalop, Geometric Algebra computations or algorithms can be developed in CLUScript. Gaalop plugins can translate or compile the CLUScript into other programming languages or codes for applications or visualizations. Gaalop is a tool that enables Geometric Algebra to be used as a practical unified mathematical language for science and engineering applications. Gaalop allows the user to define and use arbitrary Geometric Algebras $\mathcal{G}_{p,q,r}$ of p positive-signature vector-units, q negative-signature vector-units, and r null vector-units. Gaalop comes preconfigured to support many well-known Geometric Algebras that have been introduced in papers and books. $\mathcal{G}_{8,2}$ DCGA, being introduced only now in this paper, was unknown and therefore not preconfigured in Gaalop at the time of writing this paper.

The remainder of this section shows how to define DCGA in Gaalop 2.0.1⁴ and then to visualize some of the DCGA entities using the Visualizer plugin.

A.1 Definition of new algebras with definition.csv

Following Steinmetz's thesis [21], to define further algebras in Gaalop, we start by creating a folder, which we can call `algebras`, to hold subfolders for each algebra we want to define. Next, we create the subfolder `algebras/DCGA` to hold the files that define the DCGA algebra. The first file we must create is `algebras/DCGA/definition.csv`, which must contain the following 5 lines (the 2nd and 5th lines are blank):

```
1, e1, e2, e3, e4, e5, e6, e7, e8, e9, e10
```

```
1, e1, e2, e3, e4, e5, e6, e7, e8, e9, e10  
e1=1, e2=1, e3=1, e4=1, e5=-1, e6=1, e7=1, e8=1, e9=1, e10=-1
```

A.2 CLUScript macro definitions in macros.clu

The `definition.csv` file only defines the generic $\mathcal{G}_{8,2}$ Geometric Algebra basis vectors. The next file we must create is `algebras/DCGA/macros.clu`, which contains CLUScript macro/function definitions that define everything else that is specific to DCGA:

⁴Our GAALOP scripts for DCGA were written for GAALOP version 2.0.1 and may require some changes to be compatible with later versions of GAALOP. The current and older versions of GAALOP can be downloaded from <http://www.gaalop.de/download/> and from <https://github.com/CallForSanity/Gaalop>.

```

// DCGA macros.clu
// CGA1, CGA2, and DCGA origin and infinity points
eo1 = \{ (1/2)*(-e4+e5) \}
eo2 = \{ (1/2)*(-e9+e10) \}
ei1 = \{ e4+e5 \}
ei2 = \{ e9+e10 \}
eo = \{ eo1()^eo2() \}
ei = \{ ei1()^ei2() \}

// DCGA point value-extraction operators
// for defining DCGA IPNS bivector entities
Tx = \{ (1/2)*(e1^ei2()+ei1()^e6) \}
Ty = \{ (1/2)*(e2^ei2()+ei1()^e7) \}
Tz = \{ (1/2)*(e3^ei2()+ei1()^e8) \}
Txy = \{ (1/2)*(e7^e1+e6^e2) \}
Tyz = \{ (1/2)*(e7^e3+e8^e2) \}
Tzx = \{ (1/2)*(e8^e1+e6^e3) \}
Txx = \{ e6^e1 \}
Tyy = \{ e7^e2 \}
Tzz = \{ e8^e3 \}
Txt2 = \{ e1^eo2()+eo1()^e6 \}
Tyt2 = \{ e2^eo2()+eo1()^e7 \}
Tzt2 = \{ e3^eo2()+eo1()^e8 \}
T1 = \{ -ei() \}
Tt2 = \{ eo2()^ei1()+ei2()^eo1() \}
Tt4 = \{ -4*eo() \}

// Commutator and anti-commutator
com = \{ (1/2)*(_P(1)*_P(2)-_P(2)*_P(1)) \}
acom = \{ (1/2)*(_P(1)*_P(2)+_P(2)*_P(1)) \}

// Derivative operators
Dx = \{ 2*Tx()/Txx() \}
Dy = \{ 2*Ty()/Tyy() \}
Dz = \{ 2*Tz()/Tzz() \}
// Directional Derivative operator
// Try com(Dn,E) on a quadric surface entity E to
// make an entity representing the directional derivative.
Dn = \{
  x = _P(1); y = _P(2); z = _P(3); mag = sqrt(x*x+y*y+z*z);
  nx = x/mag; ny = y/mag; nz = z/mag;
  nx*Dx() + ny*Dy() + nz*Dz()
\}
// Directional Pseudo-Antiderivative operators
// Try com(In,E) on a linear entity.
// Integration constant can be added after as C*T1.
// Txt2,Tyt2,Tzt2 are pseudo-inverses of Tx,Ty,Tz
Ix = \{ Txt2()/Txx()/2 \}
Iy = \{ Tyt2()/Tyy()/2 \}
Iz = \{ Tzt2()/Tzz()/2 \}

```

```

In = \{
  x = _P(1); y = _P(2); z = _P(3); mag = sqrt(x*x+y*y+z*z);
  nx = x/mag; ny = y/mag; nz = z/mag;
  nx*Ix() + ny*Iy() + nz*Iz()
\}

// Pseudoscalars
IE1 = \{ e1^e2^e3 \}
IE2 = \{ e6^e7^e8 \}
IC1 = \{ e1^e2^e3^e4^e5 \}
IC2 = \{ e6^e7^e8^e9^e10 \}
ID = \{ e1^e2^e3^e4^e5^e6^e7^e8^e9^e10 \}

// DCGA dualization macro
DD = \{ -_P(1).ID() \}
// CGA1 and CGA2 dualizations
C1D = \{ -_P(1).IC1() \}
C2D = \{ -_P(1).IC2() \}
// Euclidean 1 and Euclidean 2 dualizations
E1D = \{ -_P(1).IE1() \}
E2D = \{ -_P(1).IE2() \}
// special Dual macro for DCGA dualization operator *
Dual = \{ DD(_P(1)) \}

// Normalize a non-null vector
Normalize = \{ _P(1)/sqrt(_P(1)._P(1)) \}
// Convert degrees angle to radians
Deg2Rad = \{ _P(1)*acos(-1)/180 \}

// CGA1_Point(x,y,z) representing point at (x,y,z) in Euclidean 3D
CGA1_Point = \{
  _P(1)*e1 + _P(2)*e2 + _P(3)*e3 +
  (1/2)*(_P(1)*_P(1) + _P(2)*_P(2) + _P(3)*_P(3))*ei1() + eo1()
\}
// CGA2_Point(x,y,z) representing point at (x,y,z) in Euclidean 3D
CGA2_Point = \{
  _P(1)*e6 + _P(2)*e7 + _P(3)*e8 +
  (1/2)*(_P(1)*_P(1) + _P(2)*_P(2) + _P(3)*_P(3))*ei2() + eo2()
\}
// special DCGA createPoint macro
createPoint = \{
  CGA1_Point(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3))^CGA2_Point(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3)) \}
DCGA_Point = \{ createPoint(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3)) \}
Normalize_CGA1_Point = \{ _P(1)/(-_P(1).ei1()) \}
Normalize_CGA2_Point = \{ _P(1)/(-_P(1).ei2()) \}
Normalize_DCGA_Point = \{ _P(1)/(-_P(1).ei()) \}
// Embed vector as CGA1 point (shorter name for CGA1_Point)
EV1 = \{ CGA1_Point(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3)) \}
// Embed vector as CGA2 point (shorter name for CGA2_Point)
EV2 = \{ CGA2_Point(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3)) \}

```

```

// Embed vector as DCGA point (shorter name for DCGA_Point)
EV = \{ DCGA_Point(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3)) \}
// Project CGA1 point back to a vector in Euclidean 1 space
PV1 = \{ -(Normalize_CGA1_Point(_P(1)).IE1()).IE1() \}
// Project CGA2 point back to a vector in Euclidean 2_ space
PV2 = \{ -(Normalize_CGA2_Point(_P(1)).IE2()).IE2() \}
// Project DCGA point back to a vector in Euclidean 1 space
PV = \{ PV1(_P(1).ei2()) \}

// Rotor(x,y,z,a) with axis (x,y,z) and rotation angle a in _degrees_
CGA1_Rotor = \{ t = Deg2Rad(_P(4));
  cos(t/2) + sin(t/2)*E1D(Normalize(_P(1)*e1 + _P(2)*e2 + _P(3)*e3))
\}
CGA2_Rotor = \{ t = Deg2Rad(_P(4));
  cos(t/2) + sin(t/2)*E2D(Normalize(_P(1)*e6 + _P(2)*e7 + _P(3)*e8))
\}
Rotor = \{
  CGA1_Rotor(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3),_P(4))^CGA2_Rotor(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3),_P(4))
\}
// Dilator(d) with scalar dilation factor d
CGA1_Dilator = \{ (1/2)*(1+_P(1)) + (1/2)*(1-_P(1))*(ei1()^eo1()) \}
CGA2_Dilator = \{ (1/2)*(1+_P(1)) + (1/2)*(1-_P(1))*(ei2()^eo2()) \}
Dilator = \{ CGA1_Dilator(_P(1))^CGA2_Dilator(_P(1)) \}
// Translator(x,y,z) for translation by displacement vector (x,y,z)
CGA1_Translator = \{ 1 - (1/2)*(_P(1)*e1+_P(2)*e2+_P(3)*e3)*ei1() \}
CGA2_Translator = \{ 1 - (1/2)*(_P(1)*e6+_P(2)*e7+_P(3)*e8)*ei2() \}
Translator = \{
  CGA1_Translator(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3))^CGA2_Translator(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3))
\}

// Ellipsoid(px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz) with center (px,py,pz), radii rx ry rz
Ellipsoid = \{
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*_P(1)*Tx()/rxSq + -2*_P(2)*Ty()/rySq + -2*_P(3)*Tz()/rzSq +
  Txx()/rxSq + Tyy()/rySq + Tzz()/rzSq +
  (pxSq/rxSq + pySq/rySq + pzSq/rzSq - 1)*T1()
\}
// Toroid(R,r) with major radius R and minor radius r
Toroid = \{
  R = _P(1); r = _P(2); dSq = R*R - r*r;
  Tt4() + 2*Tt2()*dSq + T1()*dSq*dSq - 4*R*R*(Txx()+Tyy())
\}
// Sphere(x,y,z,r) with center point (x,y,z) and radius r
CGA1_Sphere = \{ CGA1_Point(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3)) - (1/2)*_P(4)*_P(4)*ei1() \}
CGA2_Sphere = \{ CGA2_Point(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3)) - (1/2)*_P(4)*_P(4)*ei2() \}
Sphere = \{
  CGA1_Sphere(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3),_P(4))^CGA2_Sphere(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3),_P(4))
\}
// Plane(nx,ny,nz,d) with normal (nx,ny,nz) at distance d from origin

```

```

CGA1_Plane = \{ Normalize(_P(1)*e1 + _P(2)*e2 + _P(3)*e3) + _P(4)*ei1() \}
CGA2_Plane = \{ Normalize(_P(1)*e6 + _P(2)*e7 + _P(3)*e8) + _P(4)*ei2() \}
Plane = \{
  CGA1_Plane(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3),_P(4))^CGA2_Plane(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3),_P(4))
\}
// Line(px,py,pz,dx,dy,dz) through (px,py,pz) in direction of (dx,dy,dz)
CGA1_Line = \{
  d = Normalize(_P(4)*e1 + _P(5)*e2 + _P(6)*e3); D = E1D(d);
  p = _P(1)*e1 + _P(2)*e2 + _P(3)*e3; D - (p.D)*ei1()
\}
CGA2_Line = \{
  d = Normalize(_P(4)*e6 + _P(5)*e7 + _P(6)*e8); D = E2D(d);
  p = _P(1)*e6 + _P(2)*e7 + _P(3)*e8; D - (p.D)*ei2()
\}
Line = \{
  CGA1_Line(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3),_P(4),_P(5),_P(6))^
  CGA2_Line(_P(1),_P(2),_P(3),_P(4),_P(5),_P(6))
\}

// Cylinder(px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz) with center (px,py,pz) and radii rx ry rz
CylinderX = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*py*Ty()/rySq + -2*pz*Tz()/rzSq + Tyy()/rySq + Tzz()/rzSq +
  (pySq/rySq + pzSq/rzSq - 1)*T1()
\}
CylinderY = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*px*Tx()/rxSq + -2*pz*Tz()/rzSq + Txx()/rxSq + Tzz()/rzSq +
  (pxSq/rxSq + pzSq/rzSq - 1)*T1()
\}
CylinderZ = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*px*Tx()/rxSq + -2*py*Ty()/rySq + Txx()/rxSq + Tyy()/rySq +
  (pxSq/rxSq + pySq/rySq - 1)*T1()
\}

// Cone(px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz) with center (px,py,pz) and radii rx ry rz
ConeX = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  2*(px*Tx()/rxSq - py*Ty()/rySq - pz*Tz()/rzSq) -
  Txx()/rxSq + Tyy()/rySq + Tzz()/rzSq + (pySq/rySq +
  pzSq/rzSq - pxSq/rxSq)*T1()
\}

```

```

\}
ConeY = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  2*(py*Ty()/rySq - pz*Tz()/rzSq - px*Tx()/rxSq) +
  Txx()/rxSq - Tyy()/rySq + Tzz()/rzSq + (pxSq/rxSq -
  pySq/rySq + pzSq/rzSq)*T1()
\}
ConeZ = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  2*(pz*Tz()/rzSq - py*Ty()/rySq - px*Tx()/rxSq) +
  Txx()/rxSq + Tyy()/rySq - Tzz()/rzSq + (pxSq/rxSq +
  pySq/rySq - pzSq/rzSq)*T1()
\}

// Paraboloid(px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz) with vertex (px,py,pz) and radii rx ry rz
ParaboloidX = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*pz*Tz()/rzSq - 2*py*Ty()/rySq - Tx()/rx +
  Tzz()/rzSq + Tyy()/rySq + (pzSq/rzSq + pySq/rySq + px/rx)*T1()
\}
ParaboloidY = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*px*Tx()/rxSq - 2*pz*Tz()/rzSq - Ty()/ry +
  Txx()/rxSq + Tzz()/rzSq + (pxSq/rxSq + pzSq/rzSq + py/ry)*T1()
\}
ParaboloidZ = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*px*Tx()/rxSq - 2*py*Ty()/rySq - Tz()/rz +
  Txx()/rxSq + Tyy()/rySq + (pxSq/rxSq + pySq/rySq + pz/rz)*T1()
\}

// Hyperbolic paraboloid (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz) z-axis aligned
// with center point (px,py,pz) and radii rx ry rz
HParaboloidZ = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*px*Tx()/rxSq + 2*py*Ty()/rySq - Tz()/rz +
  Txx()/rxSq - Tyy()/rySq + (pxSq/rxSq - pySq/rySq + pz/rz)*T1()
\}

```

```

// Hyperboloid of one sheet (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz) z-axis aligned
// with center point (px,py,pz) and radii rx ry rz
Hyperboloid1 = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  2*pz*Tz()/rzSq - 2*px*Tx()/rxSq - 2*py*Ty()/rySq +
  Txx()/rxSq + Tyy()/rySq - Tzz()/rzSq +
  (pxSq/rxSq + pySq/rySq - pzSq/rzSq - 1)*T1()
\}
// Hyperboloid of two sheets (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz) z-axis aligned
// with center point (px,py,pz) and radii rx ry rz
Hyperboloid2 = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  2*px*Tx()/rxSq + 2*py*Ty()/rySq - 2*pz*Tz()/rzSq -
  Txx()/rxSq - Tyy()/rySq + Tzz()/rzSq +
  (pzSq/rzSq - pxSq/rxSq - pySq/rySq - 1)*T1()
\}

// Parabolic cylinders (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz)
// with center point (px,py,pz) and radii rx ry rz
PCylinderX = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*py*Ty()/rySq - Tz()/rz + Tyy()/rySq + (pySq/rySq + pz/rz)*T1()
\}
PCylinderY = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*px*Tx()/rxSq - Tz()/rz + Txx()/rxSq + (pxSq/rxSq + pz/rz)*T1()
\}
PCylinderZ = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*px*Tx()/rxSq - Ty()/ry + Txx()/rxSq + (pxSq/rxSq + py/ry)*T1()
\}

// Hyperbolic cylinders (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz)
// with center point (px,py,pz) and radii rx ry rz
HCylinderX = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*py*Ty()/rySq + 2*pz*Tz()/rzSq + Tyy()/rySq - Tzz()/rzSq +

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      (pySq/rySq - pzSq/rzSq - 1)*T1()
\}
HCylinderY = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  2*px*Tx()/rxSq - 2*pz*Tz()/rzSq - Txx()/rxSq + Tzz()/rzSq +
  (-pxSq/rxSq + pzSq/rzSq - 1)*T1()
\}
HCylinderZ = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); pz = _P(3); rx = _P(4); ry = _P(5); rz = _P(6);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); pzSq = _P(3)*_P(3);
  rxSq = _P(4)*_P(4); rySq = _P(5)*_P(5); rzSq = _P(6)*_P(6);
  -2*px*Tx()/rxSq + 2*py*Ty()/rySq + Txx()/rxSq - Tyy()/rySq +
  (pxSq/rxSq - pySq/rySq - 1)*T1()
\}

// Parallel planes pair (p1,p2) with planes a=p1, a=p2 perpendicular to a-axis
PPlanesX = \{ p1 = _P(1); p2 = _P(2); Txx() - (p1+p2)*Tx() + p1*p2*T1() \}
PPlanesY = \{ p1 = _P(1); p2 = _P(2); Tyy() - (p1+p2)*Ty() + p1*p2*T1() \}
PPlanesZ = \{ p1 = _P(1); p2 = _P(2); Tzz() - (p1+p2)*Tz() + p1*p2*T1() \}
// Non-parallel planes pairs (also types of cylinders)
// XPlanesX(y,z,ry,rz) x-axis aligned, with vertex (y,z) and slope (+|-)rz/ry
XPlanesX = \{
  py = _P(1); pz = _P(2); ry = _P(3); rz = _P(4);
  pySq = _P(1)*_P(1); pzSq = _P(2)*_P(2); rySq = _P(3)*_P(3); rzSq = _P(4)*_P(4);
  -2*py*Ty()/rySq + 2*pz*Tz()/rzSq + Tyy()/rySq - Tzz()/rzSq +
  (pySq/rySq - pzSq/rzSq)*T1()
\}
// XPlanesY(x,z,rx,rz) y-axis aligned, with vertex (x,z) and slope (+|-)rz/rx
XPlanesY = \{
  px = _P(1); pz = _P(2); rx = _P(3); rz = _P(4);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pzSq = _P(2)*_P(2); rxSq = _P(3)*_P(3); rzSq = _P(4)*_P(4);
  -2*px*Tx()/rxSq + 2*pz*Tz()/rzSq + Txx()/rxSq - Tzz()/rzSq +
  (pzSq/rzSq - pxSq/rxSq)*T1()
\}
// XPlanesZ(x,y,rx,ry) z-axis aligned, with vertex (x,y) and slope (+|-)ry/rx
XPlanesZ = \{
  px = _P(1); py = _P(2); rx = _P(3); ry = _P(4);
  pxSq = _P(1)*_P(1); pySq = _P(2)*_P(2); rxSq = _P(3)*_P(3); rySq = _P(4)*_P(4);
  -2*px*Tx()/rxSq + 2*py*Ty()/rySq + Txx()/rxSq - Tyy()/rySq +
  (pxSq/rxSq - pySq/rySq)*T1()
\}

// DupinCyclide(R,r1,r2) with major radius R and minor radii r1 and r2
DupinCyclide = \{
  u = (1/2)*(_P(2) + _P(3)); c = (1/2)*(_P(2) - _P(3)); a = _P(1); bSq = a*a-c*c;
  Tt4() + 2*Tt2()*(bSq-u*u) - 4*a*a*Txx() - 4*bSq*Tyy() +
  8*a*c*u*Tx() + ((bSq-u*u)*(bSq-u*u) - 4*c*c*u*u)*T1()
\}

```

```

hornedDupinCyclide = \{
  u = (1/2)*(_P(2) + _P(3)); c = (1/2)*(_P(2) - _P(3)); a = _P(1); bSq = a*a-u*u;
  Tt4() + 2*Tt2()*(bSq-c*c) - 4*a*a*Txx() - 4*bSq*Tyy() +
  8*a*c*u*Tx() + ((bSq-c*c)*(bSq-c*c) - 4*c*c*u*u)*T1()
\}

```

A.3 Creating the product table in products.csv

To finish the definition of the DCGA algebra, one more file `algebras/DCGA/products.csv` must be generated using the `ProductTableCreator`, which is an extra program that is available for download at the Gaalop homepage (<http://www.gaalop.de/download/>). When this program is run, it will ask for the definition folder `algebras/DCGA` of the algebra and then it generates `products.csv`.

A.4 Gaalop configuration

When Gaalop is run, it has a `Configure` button to access the configuration tabs of Gaalop.

In the `Algebra` tab, enter the full path to our `algebras` folder into the box titled `additionalBaseDirectory`.

It may be necessary to download the latest version of the Lightweight Java Game Library (LWJGL) [18] for use with the Gaalop Visualizer plugin. The latest LWJGL package in the version 2.x series may work. Download and decompress the LWJGL package to somewhere on your computer, then access the `Visualizer` configuration tab and set the `lwjglNativePath` to the appropriate folder within the LWJGL installation folder. The Gaalop `plugins` folder may need updated copies of the files `lwjgl.jar` and `lwjgl_util.jar` that can be copied from within the LWJGL installation.

If all other dependencies required for the Visualizer plugin are installed, then it should be possible to proceed with testing the DCGA algebra in Gaalop, and generating Visualizer renderings of the DCGA entities.

A.5 Visualizing DCGA entities

In the preceding subsections, Gaalop was configured for the DCGA algebra, and the Visualizer plugin was configured to use LWJGL for rendering. Assuming that the configuration is successful, the next step is to create your first CLUScript for developing your first Geometric Algebra Algorithms or computations in DCGA using Gaalop.

Start Gaalop, then press the `New File` button to create a new CLUScript file with any name you like. Select `Own - DCGA` in the `Algebra to use` selection box. Select `Visual Code Inserter` in the `VisualCodeInserter` selection box. Select `Table-Based Approach` in the `Optimization` selection box. Select `Visualizer` in the `CodeGenerator` selection box. Now, to get started, the following CLUScript demonstrates how to use the macros that were defined in `macros.clu`.

```

/* Demo of the DCGA algebra
 * Uncomment the lines to be visualized and press Optimize button.
 * Visualizing one line at a time is recommended on slow computers. */
// Set the drawing color, and display a variable circular toroid

```

```

//:White;:T = Toroid(R,r); /* variable inputs (R,r) */
//:P1 = createPoint(1,2,3); /* or EV(x,y,z) */
//:Red ;:S = Sphere(1,2,3,2); /* (px,py,pz,radius) */
//:Green ;:P = Plane(1,2,3,sqrt(1+4+9)); /* (nx,ny,nz,distance) */
//:Blue ;:L = Line(1,2,3,0,0,1); /* (px,py,pz,dx,dy,dz) */
//:Cyan ;:C = S^P; /* circle */
//:Magenta;:E = Ellipsoid(1,2,3,4,3,2); /* (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz) */
//:Yellow ;:e = E^P/16; /* ellipse (divide by 16 to help find zeros) */

// Geometric outer product null space (OPNS) bi-CGA entities
// (Visualizer required IPNS entities, so Dual * is taken)
// Sphere, the wedge of four surface points
//:SD = *( EV(-5,0,0)^EV(5,0,0)^EV(0,5,0)^EV(0,0,5) );
// Plane, the wedge of three plane points (not collinear) and infinity
//:PD = *( EV(-5,0,1)^EV(5,0,1)^EV(0,5,1)^ei() );
// Line, the wedge of two line points and infinity
//:LD = *( EV(-5,0,1)^EV(5,0,1)^ei() );
// Circle, the wedge of three circle points
//:CD = *( EV(-5,0,1)^EV(5,0,1)^EV(0,5,1) );

// Elliptic cylinders (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz)
//:CylX = CylinderX(0,1,0,1,2,4);
//:CylY = CylinderY(1,0,0,2,1,4);
//:CylZ = CylinderZ(1,0,0,4,2,1);
// Cones (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz)
//:CneX = ConeX(1,0,0,1,1,1);
//:CneY = ConeY(0,1,0,1,1,1);
//:CneZ = ConeZ(0,0,1,1,1,1);
// Paraboloids (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz)
//:ParX = ParaboloidX(1,0,0,1,1,1);
//:ParY = ParaboloidY(0,1,0,1,1,1);
//:ParZ = ParaboloidZ(0,0,1,1,1,1);
// Hyperbolic paraboloid z-axis aligned (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz)
//:HparZ = HParaboloidZ(0,0,1,1,1,1);
// Hyperboloid of one sheet z-axis aligned (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz)
//:Hyp1 = Hyperboloid1(0,0,1,1,1,1);
// Hyperboloid of two sheets z-axis aligned (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz)
//:Hyp2 = Hyperboloid2(0,0,1,1,1,1);
// Parabolic cylinders (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz)
//:PCylX = PCylinderX(0,0,1,1,2,4);
//:PCylY = PCylinderY(0,0,1,2,1,4);
//:PCylZ = PCylinderZ(1,0,0,2,4,1);
// Hyperbolic cylinders (px,py,pz,rx,ry,rz)
//:HCylX = HCylinderX(0,0,1,1,1,1);
//:HCylY = HCylinderY(0,0,1,1,1,1);
//:HCylZ = HCylinderZ(1,0,0,1,1,1);
// Parallel planes pair (p1,p2)
//:PPX = PPlanesX(1,2);
//:PPY = PPlanesY(1,4);
//:PPZ = PPlanesZ(1,6);

```

```

// Non-parallel planes pair
//:XPX = XPlanesX(1,1,2,1); /* (y,z,ry,rz) */
//:XPY = XPlanesY(1,1,2,1); /* (x,z,rx,rz) */
//:XPZ = XPlanesZ(1,1,2,1); /* (x,y,rx,ry) */
// Ellipse, parabola, hyperbola
//:e = CylinderZ(0,0,0,1,4,1)^Plane(0,0,1,1);
//:p = PCylinderZ(0,0,0,1,4,1)^Plane(0,0,1,1);
//:h = HCylinderZ(0,0,0,1,4,1)^Plane(0,0,1,1);

// Rotate, dilate, and translate an ellipsoid
//:ER = Rotor(0,0,1,45) * Ellipsoid(0,0,0,1,3,1) * ~Rotor(0,0,1,45);
//:ED = Dilator(2) * Ellipsoid(0,0,0,1,2,3) * ~Dilator(2);
//:ET = Translator(1,2,3) * Ellipsoid(0,0,0,2,3,4) * ~Translator(1,2,3);

// DupinCyclide and hornedDupinCyclide(R,r1,r1), also translated
//:DC = Translator(1,1,1) * DupinCyclide(3,2,1) * ~Translator(1,1,1);
//:HDC = Translator(1,1,1) * hornedDupinCyclide(3,2,1) * ~Translator(1,1,1);

// Parabolic cyclide as inversion of Toroid in Sphere centered on toroid surface
//:PC = Sphere(2,0,0,3) * Toroid(5,3) * ~Sphere(2,0,0,3);
// PC rotated 60deg around the z-axis (this computation can take a minute)
//:RPC = Rotor(0,0,1,60) * PC * ~Rotor(0,0,1,60);

// Intersection of DupinCyclide and a Plane
//:DC = DupinCyclide(3,2,1); /* try (R,r1,r2) for variable inputs R,r1,r2 */
//:PL = Plane(2,1,0,2);
//:DCPL = DC^PL; /* try large epsilon=4 in Gradient Method to see DCPL points */

```

Figure 12 shows the Gaalop Visualizer plugin renderings of a DCGA ring Dupin cyclide Φ , a standard DCGA plane Π , and their intersection entity $\Phi \wedge \Pi$. All three entities are rendered in the upper-left image. In the upper-right image, the plane rendering is disabled, showing only the cyclide and the intersection entity, which is seen only on its edge. In the lower-left image, the cyclide rendering is disabled, showing only the intersection entity, which is still seen on its edge. The lower-right image is a rotated view of the intersection entity, which clearly shows that it is a curve that cuts the cyclide exactly where the plane cut it.

Figure 12: Intersection $\Phi \wedge \Pi$ of ring Dupin cyclide Φ and plane Π

R.B. Easter, E.Hitzer, Conic and Cyclidic Sections in Double Conformal Geometric Algebra $G_{\{8,2\}}$ with Computing and Visualization using Gaalop, *Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences*, 43(1), pp. 334-357, 2019.
 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/mma.5887>